

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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DEPRESSION SCREENING IN A SKILLED NURSING FACILITY

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

National statistics show that depression rates are exceptionally high in skilled nursing facilities (SNFs). In addition, depression is more prevalent and harder to detect in patients with dementia due to the overlap of symptoms and comorbidities. To address this problem, the author implemented a depression screening protocol to improve depression detection in a SNF. This two-phased project included a Phase One where the staff will screen residents upon admission with Patient Health Questionnaire -2 (PHQ-2) and automatically refer all residents with a positive score for depression to mental health specialists. For Phase Two, all patients with cognitive impairments will be screened with Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD), a test shown to have superior specificity and sensitivity in detecting depression in patients with dementia. However, due to project delays and increasing depression incidents with COVID-19 lockdowns, the author and facility agreed that Phase One should be implemented ahead of the start of the project, and only Phase Two will be implemented as an official part of the project. Unfortunately, the COVID-19 pandemic reduced the number of potential participant pool and limited the ability to obtain written consents, rendering the sample size too small to reach significance. Preliminary results showed a discrepancy between the CSDD scores of the resident and the staff caregiver. These findings are similar to those of a previous study, alluding that the CSDD may not be optimal for depression screening in the SNF setting. However, the PHQ-2 screening implemented during the prework project discussion showed improved depression detection compared to at admission and should be considered for implementation at other facilities.

Keywords: depression screening, skilled nursing facility, Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia, Patient Health Questionnaire-2, dementia, cognitive impairment

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Background

According to the latest data from the National Center for Health Statistics, the percentage of adults with depression is an alarming 46.3% in skilled nursing facilities (Harris-Kojetin et al., 2019). As a comparison, from 2013 to 2016, approximately 8.1% of Americans 20 years and older had depression in any two weeks (Brody et al., 2018). For people older than 55, 10% to 15% have clinically significant depressive symptoms (Kok & Reynolds, 2017). For the cognitively impaired, national statistics were hard to find, but a localized study by Bergdahl et al. (2011) found that depression rates were higher in the population with dementia (43%) compared to 24% in those without dementia.

Regardless of the age of the individual, depression has a significant negative impact on daily activities and health outcomes. Over 80% of depressed adults report trouble with homelife, work, or social activities due to depression-related symptoms (Brody et al., 2018). For people with dementia, depression can present as the first sign of dementia development as well as the main cause of significant cognitive decline (Kitching, 2015). Depression also complicates the course and treatment of chronic diseases, which affect older people disproportionately due to the high prevalence of multiple comorbidities. In addition, depressed older adults experience more emergency department visits, take more medications, and have more frequent doctor visits, longer hospital stays, more behavioral problems, decreased quality of life, and an increased risk of comorbidity and mortality (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention & National Association of Chronic Disease Directors, 2009; Huang & Carpenter, 2011). These negative outcomes can be effectively reduced if depression is treated with medication and psychotherapy (Kok & Reynolds, 2017).

For timely treatment to be applied, the residents' depression must be detected first. At the time of the initial project discussion with facility staff, there was no standardized depression screening process implemented at the project site, a 105-bed skilled nursing facility (SNF.). Residents were only referred for psychiatry or psychology consult for depression evaluation if they had a history of preexisting depression diagnosis or antidepressant use upon admission. The referred residents were then evaluated by the psychologist for cognitive impairment using Brief Interview for Mental Status (BIMS) and depression using Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9). During the preplanning project discussion, both the Director of Nursing (DON) and the author agreed that a general depression screening should be started right away instead of waiting for project approval due to the high level of reported depression rate and the significant potential benefit of preventing serious negative sequelae. Therefore, the original Phase One of the project involving the use of PHQ-2 depression screening of all new admissions with automatic mental health when indicated, was implemented as a facility policy change before the start of the project. Instead, this project will focus on the original Phase Two of the planned project aimed to identify depression among cognitively impaired individuals (See Appendix A for flow chart).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to enhance depression identification in SNF residents with cognitive impairment by implementing and evaluating a standardized, evidence-based screening process. Currently, the project site has a depression screening protocol implemented with the use of PHQ-2 upon admission and PHQ-9 by a psychologist following referral. However, these screening tools were not tailored to assess those with cognitive impairments, who tend to have difficulty verbalizing their thoughts or recalling past memories. To address this problem, the author will implement the Cornell Scale for

Depression in Dementia (CSDD), a test specially designed for patients with dementia, which incorporates not only patient verbalized responses but also caregiver observations (Alexopoulos, 2002). This test may present as an advantage in the SNF setting, which has round-the-clock nursing staff who can readily report observational signs, and the scoring is less reliant on a resident's ability to verbalize their symptoms.

Objectives

1. Implement a standardized depression screening process
2. Compare results of different depression screening tools
3. Evaluate and modify the process based on project findings

Conceptual Model

A conceptual model is essential because it provides boundaries, structure, and directions, which ensures consistency and cohesiveness of the project (Bonnell & Smith, 2018). The most applicable model for this project is the Institute for Healthcare Improvement's (IHI) Model for Improvement (See Figure 1). IHI's quality improvement initiatives aim to improve a discipline by utilizing the knowledge of experts in that field to identify a targeted change in the system. In particular, the Model for Improvement is an algorithm for achieving a measurable goal of any scale, using three clarifying questions and Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles (Scoville & Little, 2014).

According to the Model for Improvement, all projects should start by answering the three fundamental questions to set a clear goal. These questions are: "What are we trying to accomplish? How will we know that a change is an improvement? What changes can we make that will result in improvement?" (Provost & Murray, 2011, p. 4). In response, the DNP project aimed to improve the depression identification of cognitively impaired residents in a skilled

nursing facility (SNF). An increase in the number of residents identified with depression compared to admission would indicate an improvement. This change for improvement implemented was an evidenced-based depression screening protocol.

Figure 1

The Model for Improvement

Note. Permission to use in Appendix L.

The next step in the Model of Improvement is the PDSA cycle. In the Plan phase, the project should consider the following questions: “Who will schedule and conduct the test? Exactly what changes will be made? Where will the test be conducted? When will the test be done? What data will be collected?” (Provost & Murray, 2011, p. 10). Following the steps, the author originally planned for a two-phased project. Phase One was implementing a PHQ-2

screening by staff nurses upon a resident's admission to the SNF, with an automatic referral for mental health services with a positive test result. According to current procedures, once referred, a psychologist would screen the resident for depression and cognitive impairments with a PHQ-9 and a BIMS test, respectively. As part of Phase Two of the project, residents with a BIMS score of 12 or below would be identified, indicating cognitive impairment, and the author would obtain the consent and administer the CSDD tests for a more targeted depression screening (See Appendix A for flow chart). The project was conducted between December 2020, to March 2021, in the 105-bed SNF. Data of past medical history and scores from screening tests, including BIMS, PHQ-2, PHQ-9, and CSDD, were collected.

In the Do phase, the process is implemented as planned, and data is collected for analysis (Provost & Murray, 2011). In the Study phase, the data analysis is completed, and results are compared with the predictions. In the Act phase, after a summarization of findings, the next cycle will be planned to adapt to changes to achieve the initial aim. For this project, delays in Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval and COVID-19 disruptions lead to the early implementation of Phase One during project prework, and the project, originally Phase Two, was implemented following IRB approval during January and February 2021. The data collected was used to compare depression identification with those upon admission and compared across different depression screening tests. Recommendations for future depression screening implementations were made using these findings.

Review of Literature

A comprehensive search of the literature was conducted in preparation for this project. The databases CINAHL, PubMed, Academic Search Premier, Psychinfo, and Google Scholar, were searched using the following search terms: "depression/depressive disorder/depressive symptoms/major depressive disorder," " screening/assessment/diagnostic tool," and "skilled nursing facility/nursing home/SNF/long term care." Only published literature in English was used. Publish date and geography were not limited due to the scarcity of depression screening studies in the target population.

Depression Diagnosis

According to the American Psychiatric Association (APA) (2013), the criteria for a major depressive disorder (MDD) diagnosis involves at least five of nine symptoms. These symptoms may include depressed mood, loss of interest, significant weight changes, sleep disturbances, fatigue, psychomotor disturbances, feelings of guilt, difficulty with concentration, or suicidal ideation (APA, 2013). In the nursing home setting, Huang and Carpenter (2011) identified key contributing factors which may cause underdiagnoses of depression in patients with dementia, such as communication and cognitive impairments, provider's focus on medical conditions, a normalization of late-life depression, a lack of training of staff, and lack of standardized depression screening process. The diagnosing of depression in older individuals can also be more difficult with the prevalence of cognitive impairment, which co-occurs with depression at a rate of 20-32% (Boyle et al., 2011).

Depression Screening

The most commonly used depression screening tool is the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9), which contains nine items that screen for depression symptoms (Maurer, 2012). The

American Geriatrics Society's recommendation for depression screening is to first screen with PHQ-2, which includes two screening items. If screened positive for depression, follow-up with a 15-item Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS-15) or the PHQ-9 (Maurer, 2012). Currently, the United States Department of Veterans Affairs (VA) and Medicare home health care already use the PHQ-2 to routinely screen for depression during intake (United States Department of Veterans Affairs, 2010; Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, 2017).

To compare the screening tests, for adults, the PHQ-2 has a sensitivity of 91.4 % and specificity of 72.23% at a score ≥ 2 , and the PHQ-9 has a sensitivity of 87% and a specificity of 87.13% at a score ≥ 10 (Mitchell et al., 2016). One study reported that for the cognitively impaired, PHQ-9 drops in specificity and positive predictive value in patients with cognitive impairment (Boyle et al., 2011). In contrast, the Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD) effectively detects depression, even in patients with cognitive impairment (Hancock & Larner, 2015). In a validity study between GDS and CSDD, Korner et al. (2006) found that CSDD is a better scale with 93% sensitivity, 97% specificity, while GDS has 82% to 90% sensitivity and 75% to 94% specificity. In addition, CSDD retained sensitivity and specificity in demented patients, while GDS diminished in sensitivity. This finding was echoed in Wongpakaran and Wongpakaran's (2012) study, which tested patients for cognitive impairment and depression. The researchers found that although both GDS-15 and CSDD were predictive of MDD regardless of cognitive abilities, but CSDD was a better predictor of MDD in patients with cognitive impairment with the lowest Mini-Mental State Exam score at 11 for severe dementia.

Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia

The CSDD is a clinician-administered 19-item depression screening tool aimed to assess signs and symptoms of depression in the domains of mood, behavior, physical signs, cyclic

functions, and ideational disturbance. Each item is scored either “a” for unable to evaluate, or zero to two, representing absent, mild or intermittent, and severe, respectively. The total score ranges 0 to 38, with a score above ten as probable Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) and a score above 18 as definite MDD (See Appendix B for complete form). This test has a sensitivity of 93% and a specificity of 97% at a score of ≥ 6 (Korner et al., 2006).

Summary

PHQ-2 has the sensitivity and specificity to be an excellent general depression screening tool for all populations. Although the current guideline also recommends follow-up tests by PHQ-9 and GDS-15, evidence shows that CSDD is a more effective test for the cognitively impaired. Using this information, the author devised an evidenced-based depression screening protocol involving a general depression screening with PHQ-2 for all residents during admission followed by CSDD screening for those with cognitive impairments to improve depression identification for SNF residents, especially those with dementia.

Methods

This DNP project aimed to improve depression identification of SNF residents by implementing and evaluating a standardized, evidence-based screening process. This section outlines the setting, sample, ethical considerations, procedures, timeline, and metrics of this project.

Setting/Sample

The project took place in a 105-bed SNF located in Whittier, California. Most residents are of Caucasian, Hispanic, or African-American descent, with a full range of socioeconomic levels, from private pay to Medi-Cal. They experienced various comorbidities and disabilities requiring either short-term rehabilitation or long-term skilled nursing care. A letter of support was obtained from the facility, allowing the project to proceed (Appendix K). Residents were qualified to participate if they had a BIMS score below 12 or were unable to be scored, indicating cognitive impairment. Residents were excluded if they were not fluent in English, unable to communicate verbally, or if the residents or their Legally Authorized Representative (LAR) refused participation.

Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, the SNF census dropped significantly from hospitalizations and discharge of many residents for safety concerns. This development left only residents with severe disabilities or health needs who could not be discharged safely. In addition to the drop in the applicant pool, COVID-19 travel restrictions and social distancing guidelines also negatively impacted the ability to contact the residents' LAR and obtain written consent. After the Institutional Review Board (IRB) issued permission on December 15, 2020, participant recruitment and data collection started and ended on February 28, 2021, when all available

participants were considered. In the final sample, six residents met the qualifications to participate. Three of the LAR gave verbal consent, but only two written consents were obtained.

Ethical Considerations

Consent Process

The California State University, Los Angeles, Institutional Review Board deemed the project to be expedited and approved on December 15, 2020. As the facility agreed to make PHQ-2 screening a standard practice, the data were obtained as part of clinical care, and explicit consent was not needed. For the residents identified as candidates for depression screening with CSDD, the LAR was contacted to obtain explicit informed consent using a script, and written consent was obtained. If the resident was cognitively intact enough to make his or her own medical decisions as indicated on the medical records, consent would be obtained from the resident. However, all participants were not cognitively intact, so resident assents were obtained following LAR consent and before CSDD screening. A separate written consent was obtained from the caregiver (See Appendices C to I for all the scripts and consent forms).

Confidentiality

In order to protect the confidentiality of the residents, the participant and caregiver were interviewed separately. De-identified data were recorded on Excel spreadsheets by code number. The CSDD was collected on a paper and pencil document, and the information was transcribed onto the Excel spreadsheet. The Excel spreadsheet and the list linking number codes and patient names were stored in a double password-protected computer file on the Team Lead's computer. The questionnaires with responses will be placed in a locked file cabinet in the Team Lead's office for three years following completion of data collection and analysis, after which they will be destroyed.

Procedures

1. Residents with a previous BIMS score lower than or equal to 12 or unable to be scored, indicating cognitive impairment, were identified through a medical records review.
2. The author obtained informed consent from the legally authorized representative (LAR) using a telephone script. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, many LARs were not within physically reachable distance or refused an in-person visit. Those LARs were sent a written consent form via email, and the signed consents were scanned back. One LAR signed written consent during a socially distanced visit with the resident.
3. Obtain written consent from the caregiver.
4. Once the consents were obtained, the author asked for resident assent and administered the CSDD to the resident and another CSDD to the caregiver.
5. Data on the residents' previous history of depression diagnosis or psychotropic use, scores of BIMS, PHQ-2, and PHQ-9 from medical records were recorded in addition to CSDD scores.
6. Analyzed collected data and evaluated the depression screening protocol.

Table 1

Project Timeline

Objectives	Proposed Timeline	Actual Timeline
Finalize depression screening protocol Obtain buy-in from the facility Obtain institutional approval letters	April to May 2020	June 17, 2020
Obtain IRB approval	May to September 2020	December 15, 2020
Implement protocol Data Collection	September to November 2020	January to February 2021
Evaluation of study Writing of the results	December 2020	March 2021

Note. Proposed timeline versus actual completion time.

Metrics

For the first metric, the numerator is depression identified by CSDD, and the denominator is the number of residents with BIMS ≤ 12 or unable to score. The second metric was the number of residents able to be scored by PHQ-9 over the number of residents with BIMS ≤ 12 or unable to score. The third metric was the number of residents with either a past history of depression diagnosis or medications over the number of residents with BIMS ≤ 12 or unable to score.

Results

Although the PHQ-2 depression screening upon admission was implemented during project prework, it was originally planned by the author, and the facility was willing to provide aggregate implementation data from July 2020 to December 2020, until COVID-19 interrupted normal facility function. De-identified aggregate data showed that of the 58 residents screened, 19 screened positive for probable major depressive disorder, and one was unable to be screened, which equals approximately 32.76% positivity rate. Some residents with positive results had no preexisting depression diagnosis or antidepressant use, meaning new referrals for psychiatry/psychology consultation were made, but the exact number was not recorded.

During the data collection period, six qualifying candidates for the CSDD screenings were identified. Of the six, three verbal consents were obtained from the residents' LAR, but only two written consents were obtained. One of the two residents had no preexisting depression diagnosis or antidepressant use, with a BIMS score of four indicates severe cognitive impairment. That resident had PHQ-2, PHQ-9, CSDD scores of zero and four implicates no present depression. Conversely, the second resident had a preexisting diagnosis of depression and psychotropic use. The BIMS score of 11 showed moderate cognitive impairment. The PHQ-2 score of 6 indicates possible MDD. The PHQ-9 score of 16 shows moderate-severe depression. The CSDD score for the resident at 16 shows probable MDD, but the CSDD filled in by the caregiver shows a score of 4, indicating no probable MDD (See Table 2 for data display). Calculations using preplanned metrics showed 50% of the tested residents were screened positive for depression with CSDD resident version and PHQ-9. Zero residents screened positive for depression with CSDD caregiver version. 50% of screened residents had preexisting MDD diagnosis and antidepressant use.

Table 2*Collected Data*

Resident	Existing MDD DX (No = 0; Yes = 1)	Existing antidepressant use (No = 0; Yes = 1)	PHQ-2 Score (0-6)	BIMS Score (0-15)	PHQ-9 Score (0-27)	CSDD – Resident (0-38)	CSDD - Caregiver (0-38)
1	0	0	0	4	0	0	4
2	1	1	6	11	16	16	4

Note. Collected data organized in a table.

Discussion

Limitations

Multiple factors led to the low number of final participants, limiting the conclusion that can be drawn from the project data. First of all, the COVID-19 epidemic reduced the number of participants due to hospitalizations, mass discharges, and increased difficulty in retrieving signed consent forms from the LARs with travel restrictions. Secondly, a significant portion of the SNF population were mostly Spanish-speakers or had significant cognitive-communication deficits and, therefore, did not qualify for project participation. Most importantly, a large proportion of LARs refused consent for participation, which further reduced the number of final participants.

The obstacle of obtaining informed consent from LARs was congruent with the findings of the Office of Technology Assessment of the United States Congress in 1992. The researchers reported that the research of special care unit residents was challenging due to the lack of resident's ability to consent and the family's reluctance to provided consent. The researchers concluded that any study requiring informed consent would likely end up with a small sample size that may not represent the entire population, and future studies would likely be designed to bypass the need of written consent and to avoid direct interaction with patients. Their findings appear to still hold true today, where most depression screening and screening tool comparison studies were conducted outside the United States. One study in United States' hospitals screened for geriatric syndromes before discharge to SNFs, which included the measures of GDS and BIMS, but this was possible because the study's IRB waived the requirement of written consents (Bell et al., 2016). Another study included using CSDD in 28 Washington state nursing homes, but the patient consent process was not disclosed (Townesley et al., 2012).

CSDD Discrepancy

Although inconclusive due to the small sample size, the caregiver CSDD scores appeared to differ from the resident CSDD resident score. This finding is similar to those of Towsley et al. (2012), in which resident CSDD score is concordant with a previous depression diagnosis, but the nurse CSDD scores were significantly lower than residents' self-report. The similarity between the staff CSDD scores for the two residents may hint at potential errors in a staff's ability to accurately recall conditions of a specific resident when they may be taking care of up to 34 residents per shift in the facility. However, more research is needed to make any solid conclusions.

PHQ-2 Depression Screening

Although not implemented officially as part of this project, the aggregate data obtained was still relevant to the project topic. The PHQ-2 screening detected that almost one-third of screened residents had a probable major depressive disorder upon admission. The additional automatic referrals for mental health services provided another avenue for patients to be seen promptly compared with the previous methods of using only previous depression diagnoses or medications to indicate mental health needs. The results echo the conclusion of Bell et al. (2016), which showed that hospital physicians miss or fail to document 33% to 95% of Geriatric Syndrome, many of which depression is a common component, prior to the patients' discharge to SNFs. This finding is also similar to Iden et al. (2014)'s results, which found 31% of residents were positive for depression with CSDD upon admission. The DON also reports that the floor nursing staff were the ones who performed the PHQ-2 screenings, with no resistance from staff or residents due to good existing rapport.

Conclusions

Although there were too few participants to form concrete conclusions, the results were trending similar to previous studies. The necessity of obtaining two CSDD tests per resident and the discrepancy between caregiver and resident CSDD scores does not support CSDD as the optimal depression screening tool for the SNF population. However, expanding the project to other SNFs is needed to obtain a large enough sample size to make definitive conclusions. Implementation of similar projects may also be beneficial for research purposes due to the scarcity of depression screening comparison studies conducted in the United States, especially for the patient population with cognitive impairments.

However, the protocol to screen all new admissions with PHQ-2 as part of the prework discussion with staff showed promising results. The PHQ-2 screening was able to detect depression that was previously undetected or untreated. With the simplicity of the test implementation and the high rates of depression shown in the facility data and previous research, all SNF residents can benefit from a PHQ-2 depression screening upon admission with automatic referrals for mental health specialists when indicated.

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APPENDIX A

Flow Chart

APPENDIX B

The Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia

Scoring system: a = unable to evaluate 0 = absent 1 = mild or intermittent 2 = severe

Mood-related Signs	a	0	1	2
Anxiety: anxious expression, ruminations, worrying	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sadness: sad expression, sad voice, tearfulness	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of reactivity to pleasant events	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Irritability: easily annoyed, short-tempered	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Behavioral Disturbance	a	0	1	2
Agitation: restlessness, hand wringing, hair pulling	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Retardation: slow movement, slow speech or slow reactions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Multiple physical complaints (Score 0 if GI symptoms only.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Loss of interest: less involved in usual activities (Score only if change occurred acutely, e.g., in less than one month.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Physical Signs	a	0	1	2
Appetite loss: eating less than usual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Weight loss (Score 2 if greater than 5 lbs. in one month.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of energy: fatigues easily, unable to sustain activities (Score only if change occurred acutely, e.g., in less than one month.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cyclic Functions	a	0	1	2
Diurnal variation of mood: symptoms worse in the morning	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Difficulty falling asleep: later than usual for this individual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Multiple awakenings during sleep	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Early morning awakening: earlier than usual for this individual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ideational Disturbance	a	0	1	2
Suicide: feels life is not worth living, has suicidal wishes, makes suicide attempt	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Poor self-esteem: self-blame, self-depreciation, feelings of failure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pessimism: anticipation of the worst	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mood-congruent delusions: delusions of poverty, illness or loss	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Note. Permission to use obtain from author, George Alexopoulos, MD.

APPENDIX C

LAR Consent Form

EXPEDITED CONSENT FORM

Depression Screening in a Skilled Nursing Facility
To the Resident's Legally Authorized Representative:

The resident for whom you are the Legally Authorized Representative (LAR) is invited to take part in a research project conducted by Wanting Tan, a doctoral student working with Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, an Associate Professor at California State University, Los Angeles. In this study, we hope to learn more about depression screening of residents with cognitive impairment. The resident is invited to participate in this study because of a positive screening for possible cognitive impairment during an assessment by a psychologist. We hope that our research will lead to the establishment of an effective standardized depression screening process for residents with cognitive impairment using the Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD). The resident must be at least 18 years of age or older to participate.

If you agree to have the resident participate, the resident will be asked questions. The interview process may take 30 minutes for the resident to complete. The questions will be related to the resident's mood, behavior, physical and psychological state, and whether the resident experiences change in how he/she feels across the course of the day. They may refrain from answering any questions that make them feel uncomfortable. We will also go into the resident's medical record to obtain whether or not the resident has a history of depression, past antidepressant use, and scores from previous depression screening with Patient Health Questionnaire -2 (PHQ-2), Patient Health Questionnaire -9 (PHQ-9), and cognitive screening with Brief Interview for Mental Status (BIMS).

There are minimal risks to this study. The resident may be uncomfortable responding to some of the questions. Because I am a provider, the resident may feel like they have to participate. The resident can refuse to respond to any questions or ask to take breaks without penalty, and the resident can ask me to stop at any time. The resident's participation is voluntary, and if they don't want to participate, they do not have to. The resident can withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. There is also a risk of loss of confidentiality of medical record information. To reduce this risk, only data without the resident's name will be entered into the data collection sheet.

Reports resulting from this study will not identify the resident as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission as the legally authorized representative or as required by law. If you give us permission by signing this consent form, we will protect the resident's confidentiality. None of the resident's identifying information will be put on the data collection tool. Sequential numbers will be used to identify the resident. There will be a sheet kept separately with the code number and the resident's name. Only aggregated de-identified data will be reported. The consent forms and questionnaires will be stored in a locked cabinet in Dr. Winokur's office at California State University, Los Angeles. The folder will be sealed and will be destroyed three years from the date of the last record collected. The information will be kept in a double password-protected file in Dr. Winokur's computer. In addition, as health care workers, we are obliged under California law to report any abuse that we encounter or reasonably suspect.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call Wanting Tan at [REDACTED], or write her at [REDACTED]. You may also contact the Faculty Advisor, Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, at [REDACTED], or write her at [REDACTED].

By signing this consent form, you indicate that you have read the form and agree to allow [REDACTED] to participate in the study. If you choose not to take part, there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which the resident is entitled. If you agree to allow the resident to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time.

I agree to allow the resident, _____, to participate in Depression Screening in a Skilled Nursing Facility, as set out above.

Print Resident Name

Date

Print Legally Authorized Representative Name

Signature Legally Authorized Representative

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN REVIEWED BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH. ADDITIONAL CONCERNS AND COMPLAINTS, OR QUESTIONS REGARDING YOUR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT, SHOULD BE DIRECTED TO THE ASSOCIATE VICE PRESIDENT FOR RESEARCH (Phone number: 323-343-5368).

APPENDIX D

Caregiver Consent Form

EXPEDITED CONSENT FORM

Depression Screening in a Skilled Nursing Facility
To the Resident's Caregiver:

You are invited to participate in a research project conducted by Wanting Tan, a doctoral student working with Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, an Associate Professor at California State University, Los Angeles, because you are the caregiver for a resident who has agreed to participate in this study. In this study, we hope to learn more about depression screening of residents with cognitive impairment. The resident is invited to participate in this study because of a positive screening for possible cognitive impairment during an assessment by a psychologist. We hope that our research will lead to the establishment of an effective standardized depression screening process for residents with cognitive impairment using the Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD). You must be at least 18 years of age or older to participate.

If you agree to participate, you will be asked questions. The interview process may take 15 minutes to complete. The questions will be related to the resident's mood, behavior, physical and psychological state, and whether the resident experiences changes in how he/she feels across the course of the day.

There are minimal risks to this study. You may feel uncomfortable answer questions, and you may refuse to answer any questions you're not comfortable answering. Because I am a provider at the site, you may feel like you must participate. This is not the case. Participation is voluntary, and declining to participate will have no impact on your employment. Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as providing any data. All information gathered from you in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you give us permission by signing this consent form, we will protect your confidentiality. Your identifying information will not be placed in the data collection tool. Only aggregated de-identified data will be reported. The consent forms and questionnaires will be stored in a locked cabinet in Dr. Winokur's office in California State University, Los Angeles. The folder will be sealed and will be destroyed three years from the date of the last record collected. The information will be kept in a double password-protected file in Dr. Winokur's computer. In addition, as health care workers, we are obliged under California law to report any abuse that we encounter or reasonably suspect.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call Wanting Tan at [REDACTED], or write her at [REDACTED]. You may also contact the Faculty Advisor, Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, at [REDACTED], or write her at [REDACTED].

By signing this consent form, you indicate that you have read the form and agree voluntarily to participate in the study. If you choose not to take part, there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. If you agree to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time. Likewise, no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled will occur.

I agree to participate in Depression Screening in a Skilled Nursing Facility, as set out above.

Print Caregiver Name

Date

Signature Caregiver

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN REVIEWED BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH. ADDITIONAL CONCERNS AND COMPLAINTS, OR QUESTIONS REGARDING YOUR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT, SHOULD BE DIRECTED TO THE ASSOCIATE VICE PRESIDENT FOR RESEARCH (Phone number: 323-343-5368).

APPENDIX E

Participant Consent Form

EXPEDITED CONSENT FORM

Depression Screening in a Skilled Nursing Facility
To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by Wanting Tan, a doctoral student working with Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, an Associate Professor at California State University, Los Angeles. In this study, we hope to learn more about depression screening of residents with cognitive impairment. You are invited to participate in this study because of a positive screening for possible cognitive impairment during an assessment by a psychologist. We hope that our research will lead to the establishment of an effective standardized depression screening process for residents with cognitive impairment using the Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD). You must be at least 18 years of age or older to participate.

If you agree to participate, you will be asked questions. The interview process may take 30 minutes to complete. The questions will be related to your mood, behavior, physical and psychological state, and whether you experience changes in how you feel across the course of the day. You may refrain from answering any questions that make you feel uncomfortable. We will also go into your medical record to obtain whether or not you have a history of depression, past antidepressant use, and scores from previous depression screening with Patient Health Questionnaire -2 (PHQ-2), Patient Health Questionnaire -9 (PHQ-9), and cognitive screening with Brief Interview for Mental Status (BIMS).

There are minimal risks to this study. You may be uncomfortable responding to some of the questions. Because I am a provider, you may feel like you have to participate. You can refuse to respond to any questions or ask to take breaks without penalty and you can ask me to stop at any time. Your participation is voluntary and if you don't want to participate, you do not have to. You can withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. There is also a risk of loss of confidentiality of medical record information. To reduce this risk, only data without the your name will be entered onto the data collection sheet.

Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you give us permission by signing this consent form, we will protect your confidentiality. None of your identifying information will be put on the data collection tool. Sequential numbers will be used to identify you. There will be a sheet kept separately with the code number and your name. Only aggregated de-identified data will be reported. The consent forms and questionnaires will be stored in a locked cabinet in Dr. Winokur's office at California State University, Los Angeles. The folder will be sealed and will be destroyed three years from the date of the last record collected. The information will be kept in a double password-protected file in Dr. Winokur's computer. In addition, as health care workers, we are obliged under California law to report any abuse that we encounter or reasonably suspect.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call Wanting Tan at [REDACTED], or write her at [REDACTED]. You may also contact the Faculty Advisor, Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, at [REDACTED], or write her at [REDACTED].

By signing this consent form, you indicate that you have read the form and agree voluntarily to participate in the study. If you choose not to take part, there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. If you agree to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time. Likewise, no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled will occur.

I agree to participate in Depression Screening in a Skilled Nursing Facility, as set out above.

Print Resident Name

Date

Signature of Resident

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN REVIEWED BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH. ADDITIONAL CONCERNS AND COMPLAINTS, OR QUESTIONS REGARDING YOUR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT, SHOULD BE DIRECTED TO THE ASSOCIATE VICE PRESIDENT FOR RESEARCH (Phone number: 323-343-5368).

APPENDIX F

Telephone Recruitment Script for LAR

Telephone Recruitment Script for Legally Authorized Representative:

Hello, my name is Wanting Tan. I am a Doctor of Nursing Practice student working with Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, an Associate Professor at Cal State LA, to conduct a quality improvement project involving the depression screening of skilled nursing facility residents with possible cognitive impairment. The resident for whom you are the Legally Authorized Representative (LAR) is invited to participate in this study because of a positive screening for possible cognitive impairment during an assessment by a psychologist. We hope that our research will lead to the establishment of an effective standardized depression screening process for residents with cognitive impairment using the Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD). The CSDD is a validated depression screening tool meant for the cognitively impaired. Participants in this project will answer questions related to the resident's mood, behavior, physical and psychological state, and whether they experience changes in how they feel across the course of the day. These questions may take about 30 minutes for the resident. They may refrain from answering any questions that make them feel uncomfortable. I will be comparing the results to the current method of using the Patient Health Questionnaire-2 (PHQ-2), Patient Health Questionnaire – 9 (PHQ-9) and Brief Interview For Mental Status (BIMS), which I will be retrieving from the resident's medical record. Participation is voluntary. If you choose not to participate, the resident will not lose any of the benefits for care to which he/she is entitled. If you are interested in having the resident participate, I will go over the consent with you, and I will be sharing the results of the screening with you. If you need to contact me later, you can reach me at

[REDACTED] . You may also contact Dr. Winokur at

APPENDIX G

In-Person Participant Recruitment Script

In-Person Participant Recruitment Script

Hello, my name is Wanting Tan. I am a Doctor of Nursing Practice student working with Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, an Associate Professor at Cal State LA, to conduct a project involving the depression screening of skilled nursing facility residents with possible cognitive impairment. You are invited to participate in this study because of a positive screening for possible cognitive impairment during an assessment by a psychologist. We hope that our research will lead to the establishment of an effective standardized depression screening process for residents with cognitive impairment using the Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD). The CSDD is a validated depression screening tool meant for the cognitively impaired. Participants in this project, as well as their staff caretakers, will answer the CSDD questions separately. The questions will be related to the your mood, behavior, physical and psychological state, and whether you experience changes in how you feel across the course of the day. These questions should take up to 30 minutes to complete. You may refrain from answering any questions that make you feel uncomfortable. I will be comparing the results to the current method of using the Patient Health Questionnaire-2 (PHQ-2), Patient Health Questionnaire – 9 (PHQ-9) and Brief Interview For Mental Status (BIMS), which I will be retrieving from your medical record. Participation is voluntary. If you choose not to participate, you will not lose any of the benefits or care to which you are entitled. If you are interested in participating, I will go over the consent with you, and I will be sharing the results of the screening with you. If you need to contact me later, you can reach me at [REDACTED] You may also contact Dr. Winokur at [REDACTED]

APPENDIX H

Caregiver Script

Caregiver Script

Hello, my name is Wanting Tan. I am a Doctor of Nursing Practice student working with Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, an Associate Professor at Cal State LA, to conduct a project involving the depression screening of skilled nursing facility residents with possible cognitive impairment. You are invited to participate in this study because you provide care to residents who had a positive screening for possible cognitive impairment during an assessment by a psychologist. We hope that our research will lead to the establishment of an effective standardized depression screening process for residents with cognitive impairment using the Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD). The CSDD is a validated depression screening tool meant for the cognitively impaired. You, as the staff caregiver, will answer the CSDD questions. The questions will be related to the residents' mood, behavior, physical and psychological state, and whether you think they experience changes in how they feel across the course of the day. These questions should take up to 15 minutes for you. You may refrain from answering any questions that make you feel uncomfortable. Participation is voluntary. If you choose not to participate, you will not lose any of the benefits to which you are entitled. If you are interested in participating, I will go over the consent with you. If you need to contact me later, you can reach me at [REDACTED]. You may also contact Dr. Winokur at [REDACTED].

APPENDIX I

Participant Assent Script

Assent Script

Hello, my name is Wanting Tan. I am a Doctor of Nursing Practice student. I am working with Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, an Associate Professor at Cal State LA. We are doing a depression screening project for people living in skilled nursing facility with possible dementia. You are invited to take part because your regular check by a psychologist showed a lower score. We want to see if the Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD) is a good tool when compared to others you had before. First, I will go to your medical chart to get the scores and information about possible depression. Then both you and the people taking care of you will answer questions in the CSDD. These questions ask about how you feel, how you act, and what you think about throughout the day. These questions take 30 minutes. You may choose not to take part or answer any questions that you do not like. Your care will not change for the worse no matter what you choose. I will let you and your legally guardian know the result of the test. If you need to contact me later, you can reach me at [REDACTED] You may also contact Dr. Winokur at [REDACTED]

APPENDIX J

IRB Approval Letter

Office Memorandum

DATE:	December 15, 2020
TO:	Elizabeth Winokur
FROM:	California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB
PROJECT TITLE:	[1627443-1] Depression Screening In a Skilled Nursing Facility
REFERENCE #:	19-227
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	APPROVED
APPROVAL DATE:	December 15, 2020
EXPIRATION DATE:	December 15, 2021
NEXT REPORT DUE DATE:	N/A
REVIEW TYPE:	Expedited Review
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Expedited review categories 5 and 7

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has APPROVED your submission. This approval is based on an appropriate risk/benefit ratio and a project design wherein the risks have been minimized. All research must be conducted in accordance with this approved submission.

This submission has received Expedited Review based on the applicable federal regulations.

This project has been determined to be a MINIMAL RISK project. Based on the following risks - because the study involves vulnerable participants, including those with physical disabilities and impaired decision-making capacity - this project requires continuing review by this committee on an annual basis. Your documentation for continuing review must be received 30 days before December 15, 2021 to allow sufficient time for review and continued approval.

Please make sure that you follow the procedures for informed consent outlined in the APPROVED proposal as required by federal regulations.

Please note that any modification to previously approved materials must be approved by this committee prior to initiation. Please use the appropriate modification forms for this procedure.

All UNANTICIPATED PROBLEMS involving risks to subjects or others and SERIOUS and UNEXPECTED adverse events must be reported promptly to irb@calstatela.edu using the "Adverse Event Form." All federal and sponsor reporting requirements should also be followed.

- 1 -

Generated on IRBNet

All NON-COMPLIANCE issues or COMPLAINTS regarding this project must be reported promptly to this office.

Please note that all research records must be retained for a minimum of three years after the completion of the project.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Elia Amaro. It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

APPENDIX K**Institutional Approval Letter****Whittier Pacific
Care Center***Commitment to Excellence***Institutional Approval Letter**

June 17, 2020

To Whom It May Concern:

I understand and hereby give permission for Wanting Tan to conduct a quality improvement project at Whittier Pacific Care Center. Permission will be given for the following activities:

- (1) collection and/or receipt of deidentified data on the quantity of residents with preexisting depression diagnosis and/or use of psychotropic medication, referral to mental health specialists, as well as cognitive and depression screening scores.
- (2) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to her project, including obtaining consent from the residents or their legally authorized representatives, and conducting depression screening.

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research-related regulations. I am aware that this data in de-identified, aggregated format will be used in her Doctor of Nursing Capstone Project.

Penie Manalo, RN, BSN
Director of Nursing Services

APPENDIX L

Publisher Permission for the Model for Improvement

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TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Mar 16, 2021

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Will you be translating?	No
Title	DNP Student
Institution name	California State University, Los Angeles
Expected presentation date	Apr 2021

APPENDIX L**Author Permission for CSDD**

George S Alexopoulos <gsalexop@med.cornell.edu>

Fri 4/3/2020 2:22 AM

To: Wanting Tan <wtan7@csu.fullerton.edu>

You have my permission.

G. Alexopoulos